

Relation Between Lattice Energy and Melting Point of Some Crystalline Substances. Some Transition Metals

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The study of well-established approximate constancy of the ratio of the lattice energy, $-U_0$, to the absolute melting point, T_m , i.e., $-U_0/T_m$, in similar crystalline substances has been extended to some transition metals. This has been made possible by a new approach for the calculation of the lattice energy of transition metals, viz., by using the number of 'metallic valency electrons, 'v', as given by Pauling⁶ instead of the usual practice of using the number of chemical valency electrons for 'n' in the equation:

$$-U_0 = I \times n + S$$

(I is the first ionisation potential and S , the latent heat of sublimation of the metal concerned). The equation seems to provide, in general, reasonably correct values of the lattice energies of several heavier metals. The limitations of the equation have been discussed.

Proportionality relationship between the lattice energy, $-U_0$, and the corresponding absolute melting point, T_m , was reported to exist in a number of systems of similar substances including alkali and alkaline earth metals'. Further attempts to extend this study to other metals, specially of transition series, were not successful on account of the lack of reliable data on the lattice energies of these metals⁶. The lattice energy, $-U_0$, of a metal can be calculated from the equation:

$$-U_0 = I \times n + S \quad (1)$$

where I being the first ionisation potential, 'n', the number of valency electrons, and S , the latent heat of sublimation of the metal concerned. The values of $-U_0$, obtained from equation (1), agree with the lattice energy data from other sources^{2,3} and correspond with the properties in the case of alkali and alkaline earth metals. Equation (1) fails completely in metals like Cu, Ag, Au, etc., where the number of valency electrons is only one, but $-U_0$ must be appreciably larger than those of the alkali metals as shown by the marked difference in their physical properties. The values of $-U_0$ obtained from Wilson's equations⁴, namely,

$$\begin{aligned} -U_0 &= 1.581 Ne^2/r \text{ (for body-centered cubic lattice) and} \\ -U_0 &= 1628 Ne^2/r \text{ (for face-centered cubic lattice)} \end{aligned}$$

are also very low and unsatisfactory because it will be difficult to explain the difference in the physical properties of metals like alkali and alkaline earths, on the one hand, and

*Doubts have been expressed about the accuracy of $-U_0$ data published in a few cases (see ref. 3).

1. Ram Gopal, this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 55; *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1955, 278, 42; 281, 217; 279, 220; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, 53, 406.

2. Rice, "Electronic Structure and Chemical Binding", McGraw Hill Book Company, New York, 1940, p. 370.

3. Ketselaar, "Chemical Constitution", 2nd ed., Elsevier Publishing Company, London, 1958, p. 322.

4. Wilson, "Theory of Metals", Cambridge, 1936, 1953.

those of transition metals, on the other, on the slight difference in the lattice energies obtained from any one of the above procedures. This hopeless situation has been realised by Ketelaar³ who sums up the position thus: ". . . . However, it is certain that 3d electrons contribute, to an important extent, to the cohesion in transition metals with their low volatility. In contrast, Mott and Jones², on the basis of the band theory, assumed that the bonding is determined essentially by 4s electrons and even less than one electron (per atom). This would make the transition metals comparable to alkali metals in lattice energy and volatility which is completely wrong"*

A reproduction of the values of $-U_0$ from Ketelaar's book³ (Table I) is very instructive from this point of view.

TABLE I

Metal.	$-U_0$ (K e a l s.).		Metal.	$-U_0$ [K e a l s.).	
	Calc.†	Obs.††		Calc.†	Obs.††
Li	175.0	161.5	Mg	..	558
Na	143.0	144.5	Be	..	712
K	113.0	121.5	Cu	211.0	260
Rb	107.5	116.6	Ag	187.0	244
Cs	100.0	108.7	Au	187.5	302
Ca	..	487.0	Zn	..	662
Sr	..	424.0	Cd	..	624
Ba	..	392.0	Hg	..	689

† From Wilson's equation.

†† From equation (1).

From Table I the anomalies in the situation are obvious. For example, it is simply absurd to think that $-U_0$ for Zn, Cd, and Hg with so low melting and boiling points would be more than twice as compared to those for Cu, Ag, and Au. One is therefore forced to agree with Ketelaar that these values of $-U_0$ for heavier metals are simply inadmissible. It is obvious that we have to work out a method for estimating reasonably correct values of the lattice energies, reflecting the difference in the physical properties of different metals, before examining the applicability of the $-U_0/T_m$ relationship to heavier metals.

Estimation of the Lattice Energy

Binding forces in metals are due to interaction of fixed positive nuclei and electrons. It is obvious that the strength of the bonding will depend on the number of electrons available per atom for the binding purposes. This number for normal metals is the number of valence-shell electrons, i.e., the number of chemical valency electrons. For others, specially the transition metals, this will not be the number of chemical valency electrons, as has been hitherto assumed, because the electrons of the inner *p*- and *d*-shells may also take part in the binding, over and above the *s*-shell electrons, producing among

* "The Theory of the Properties of Metals and Alloys", Oxford, 1936.

* See No. 2, p. 345.

them hybridised orbitals of the same energy. Hence such bonding electron should also be taken into account in so far as the metallic binding is concerned. The total number of electrons involved in the bonding of atoms in metals has been estimated by Pauling⁶ and we may call this number per atom as Pauling's 'metallic valency' or simply 'metallic valency'. One may denote this number by 'v' to distinguish it from 'n' or chemical valency electrons and rewrite equation (1) in the form:

$$-U_0 = I \times v + S \quad (2)$$

where 'v' is the number of 'metallic valency electrons' and not the 'chemical valency electrons', as has been assumed by workers till this time. For simplifying calculations, it may be assumed that the ionisation potential, I , for the Pauling's metallic valency electrons is approximately equal to the first ionisation potential of the metal. This is perhaps an oversimplification. It appears to be justified from the arguments presented in the foot-note. The values of $-U_0$ for several metals, calculated from equation (2), are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Metal.	I (e.V.)	v .	$S\ddot{}$ (Kcals.)	$I \times v + S$ (Kcals.)	Metal.	I (e.V.)	v .	S (Kcals.)	$I \times v + S$ (Kcals.)
Cu	7.69	5.56	81	1064	Ir	9.00	6	120	1364
Ag	7.54	5.50	68	1034	Pt	9.00	6	127	1371
Au	9.20	5.56	92	1271	Ru	7.70	6	120	1184
Fe	7.83	6.00	94	1176	Rh	7.70	6	115	1179
Co	7.81	6.00	85	1164	Pd	8.50	6	110	1284
Ni	7.61	6.00	85	1135	Cr	6.74	6	88	1020
Os	9.00	6.00	125	1369	Mo	7.35	6	160	1176
					W	8.00	6	210	1316

§From Bichowsky, and Rossini, "Thermochemistry of Chemical Substances", Reinhold Publishing Corporation, New York, 1951.

A comparison of Tables I and II clearly shows that the values of $-U_0$, obtained from equation (2), are several times larger than those quoted by Ketelaar³. In Table III the

6. Pauling, "Nature of the Chemical Bond", 3rd ed., Cornell University Press, Ithaca, New York, 1960, p. 394.

*For the purposes of calculating the binding energy, the metallic valency electrons can be thought of as moving in hybridised and localised atomic orbitals. Compare ref. 3, p. 346; also see Slater's "Introduction to Chemical Physics", McGraw Hill Book Company, New York, 1939, pp. 445, 451, 455 and 456.

†It may be argued that since the potential required to remove the successive electrons from a metal atom, i. e., successive ionisation potentials, will go on increasing, there is no justification for using the first ionisation potential, I , for all the bonding electrons, i. e. 'v'. It must be kept in mind, however, that the idea of successive ionisation potentials is applicable only to the isolated atoms. When the atoms are present in the solid metal lattice, the situation is completely different, because here the bonding electrons occupy hybridised orbitals of the same energy. Further, because in heavier transition metals, hybridisation occurs between d - and next higher s -orbitals and d -, p - and s -orbitals, the energy of the hybridised orbitals will not be very much different from that of the unhybridised s -orbital because it is one of the important conditions for hybridisation to occur. Hence the use of the first ionisation potential, I , which corresponds to the energy of the unhybridised s -orbital, seems to be quite justified (cf. ref. 3, p. 346; ref. 6, p. 304; also Slater's "Introduction to Chemical Physics", 1939, pp. 445, 451, 455 and 456).

relationship $-U_0/T_m$ for some transition metals has been examined, using ν_{max} , obtained from equation (2), and are recorded in Table II.

TABLE III

Metal.	$-U_0$.	$*T_m$.	$-U_0/T_m$.	Metal.	$-U_0$.	$*T_m$.	$-U_0/T_m$.
Cu	1064	1356°K	0.79	Ir	1364	2727	0.50
Ag	1034	1234	0.84	Pt	1371	2047	0.66
Au	1271	1330	0.95	Ru	1184	2723°K	0.44
Fe	1176	1808	0.65	Rh	1179	2230	0.52
Co	1164	1768	0.66	Pd	1284	1822	0.70
Ni	1137	1728	0.66	Cr	1020	2163	0.47
Os	1369	2973	0.46	Mo	1176	2893	0.41
				W	1310	3043	0.36

*Hodgman *et al.*, "Handbook of Chemistry and Physics", 38th ed., Chemical Rubber Publishing Company, Cleveland, Ohio, 1956-57, pp. 2113-14.

From Table III it may be observed that although the ratio $-U_0/T_m$ is not constant for all the fifteen cases examined here, it is fairly constant for the various sets of closely allied metals like iron, cobalt, and nickel etc. The very interesting fact is that the $-U_0/T_m$ values in many cases lie around 0.5, which is only slightly different from the corresponding values for alkali and alkaline earth metals¹, for which $-U_0/T_m$ lie around 0.4.

The values of $-U_0$, obtained from equation (2), appear to be less satisfactory in some cases, e.g., Pd, Mo, and W. From the expected similarity of the $-U_0/T_m$ values and in other properties, it appears that $-U_0$ for Pd is rather large and for Mo and W, rather small. Keeping in view the principle of similarity (or correspondence), one would put $-U_0$ for Pd around 900-1000 Kcals. and for Mo and W around 1400-1500 and 2000-2200 Kcals. respectively. It appears that the values of $-U_0$ for Cu, Ag, and Au, recorded in Tables II and III, are also slightly high. A number of other energy relations and physical properties of solid metals also support these estimates and suggestions. This topic we propose to discuss in our next communication.

It is obvious therefore that equation (2) gives rather crude estimates of the lattice energy $-U_0$ of heavier metals. Refinements in the procedure are clearly needed in order to obtain more accurate values. It must be appreciated, however, that it appears to be a big step towards the final solution of calculating the lattice energy of heavier metals.

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